

Table 2. Effect of root cutting at heading stage on yield and yield components of different rice varieties.^a

Variety	Treatment	Effective panicles (no. m ⁻²)	Grains per panicle (no.)	Filled grains (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Yield difference (%)
Guang-Lu-Ai	Check	300.0 a	90 a	86.4 a	25.9 a	6.0 b	0.0
	T ₁	312.5 a	94 a	88.9 a	25.5 a	6.6 a	10.2
	T ₂	282.5 b	95 a	88.5 a	25.8 a	6.1 b	1.4
	T ₃	292.5 b	94 a	87.0 a	25.4 a	6.1 b	0.6
Er-Qing-Ai	Check	270.0 a	155 a	85.1 a	23.8 a	8.5 a	0.0
	T ₁	260.0 a	143 b	78.0 b	23.9 a	6.9 b	-18.2
	T ₂	250.0 a	144 b	83.2 a	23.3 a	7.0 b	-17.7
	T ₃	270.0 a	133 c	84.2 a	24.3 a	7.4 b	-13.3
Pei-Za 72	Check	243.8 a	255 a	71.0 a	19.2 a	8.5 a	0.0
	T ₁	233.3 a	267 a	74.5 a	19.1 a	8.9 a	4.6
	T ₂	247.3 a	241 b	71.4 a	19.3 a	8.2 a	-3.1
	T ₃	225.0 b	234 b	66.7 b	19.2 a	6.7 b	-20.4
Feng-Ai Zhan I	Check	246.5 ab	214 a	63.1 b	20.6 a	6.8 a	0.0
	T ₁	247.3 ab	191 b	78.6 a	20.7 a	7.7 a	12.8
	T ₂	236.3 b	171 c	64.4 b	19.9 a	5.2 b	-24.5
	T ₃	267.8 a	189 b	52.9 c	20.2 a	5.4 b	-21.2
Te-San-Ai	Check	207.5 b	172 a	66.9 b	28.9 a	6.9 b	0.0
	T ₁	220.0 a	169 b	73.3 a	28.2 a	7.7 a	11.4
	T ₂	227.5 a	166 b	69.3 ab	28.4 a	7.4 ab	7.7
	T ₃	212.5 a	180 a	66.1 b	27.5 b	7.0 b	0.8

^aNumbers followed by different letters in a column in the same variety significantly differ at $P = 0.05$.

yield increases in two varieties (Guang-Lu-Ai, Te-San-Ai) and yield decreases in the others (Er-Qing-Ai, Pei-Za 72, Feng-Ai Zhan I).

It can be concluded that light root cutting at the heading stage has no significant effect on rice yield. It can even increase the yield of some varieties. This

may be because root cutting can increase root activity at maturity, which is important in absorbing water and nutrients and delaying plant senescence.

Equilibrium moisture content of rice and maize upon drying

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Cereal grain is ordinarily harvested at moisture contents above safe storage levels; therefore, additional drying is usually needed (Robayo and Pfof 1973). During drying, heat is necessary to evaporate moisture from the grain and a flow of air is needed to carry away the evaporated moisture (Trim and Robinson 1994).

The equilibrium moisture content (EMC) of cereal grain is important in both drying and storage because of its relationship with the relative humidity

(RH) and temperature of the air. Crop grains (including cereals) are hygroscopic and will lose or gain moisture until equilibrium is reached with the surrounding air (Henderson and Perry 1955, Trim and Robinson 1994).

This experiment observed the interaction between water and crop grain by measuring EMC as a function of RH at constant temperature. A plot of the equilibrium RH and moisture content (MC) is known as the moisture curve.

The drying experiment was conducted at RIMOC in Maros, South Sulawesi, Indonesia, to study the equation/curve of EMC by using a mechanical batch-type dryer with a grain bin in a 5-m² (2 × 2.5 m) rectangular box, 0.9 m tall, and holding 1–1.5 t of rice or maize at a depth of 0.35 m. The drying air temperature and drying air velocity were 43 °C and 50 m³ min⁻¹, respectively.

Varieties IR42 (rice) and Bisma (maize) were used in this experiment. The

following equation was based on Henderson's equation (1952):

$$1 - RH = e^{-cT EMC^n}$$

where

RH = equilibrium relative humidity (decimal),
 EMC = equilibrium moisture content (%),
 T = temperature (°C),
 c and n = constants, and
 e = 2.7182.

To calculate c and n, Henderson's equation was multiplied by ln (Robayo and Pfof 1973):

$$\ln(1 - RH) = -cT EMC^n \ln e$$

$$\ln \ln \frac{1}{1 - RH} = \ln c + \ln T + n \ln EMC$$

if

$$\ln \ln \frac{1}{1 - RH} = y$$

$$\ln c + \ln T = b$$

$$\ln EMC = x$$

$$n = a$$

to get the following equation:

$$y = b + ax$$

By using the least squares method, a, b, r (correlation coefficient between soil moisture content and relative humidity), c, and n can be found.

$$\sum y = b m + a \sum x$$

$$\sum xy = b \sum x + a \sum x^2$$

$$b = \frac{\sum y - a \sum x}{m}$$

$$a = \frac{\sum xy - \frac{\sum x \sum y}{m}}{\sum x^2 - \frac{(\sum x)^2}{m}}$$

$$r = \frac{\sum xy - \left[\frac{\sum x \sum y}{m} \right]}{\sqrt{\left[\sum x^2 - \frac{(\sum x)^2}{m} \right] \left[\sum y^2 - \frac{(\sum y)^2}{m} \right]}}$$

where

r = coefficient correlation between moisture content and relative humidity
 m = drying periods (hours = ii)

At the start of drying, RH for drying rice decreased from 92% to 79%, causing MC to decrease fast from 21.0% to 16.5% (average drying rate = 2.2% h⁻¹). For maize, RH decreased from 88% to 67%, resulting in a rapid decline of MC from 21.2% to 15.2% (average drying rate = 2.9% h⁻¹). A decrease in RH from 71% to 20% reduced MC in rice further from 14.5% to 5.6%

(drying rate = 2.0–0.6% h⁻¹), whereas a decrease in RH from 56% to 19% resulted in a decrease in MC in maize from 12.3% to 6.2% (drying rate = 2.2–0.2% h).

From the data in the table, constants c and n could be calculated: 1.92 × 10⁻⁵ and 1.76 for rice, and 2.93 × 10⁻⁵ and 1.57 for maize constants c and n values depend on the material, which affect the shape and slope of the EMC curve. The EMC for rice and maize is 5.6% and 5.2% at 20% RH, and 15.7% and 16.7% at 75% RH, respectively (see figure).

Equilibrium moisture curve for rice and maize at 43 °C (569.4 °R).

References

Henderson SM. 1952. A basic concept of equilibrium moisture. *Agric. Eng.* 33(7): 29–32.

Henderson SM, Perry RL. 1955. *Agricultural process engineering*. New York: John Wiley & Sons, Inc. p 273–301.

Robayo JF, Pfof HB. 1973. Rice drying rates. MS thesis. Food and Feed Grain Institute, Kansas State University, Manhattan, Kansas (unpubl.)

Trim DS, Robinson AP. 1994. Drying methods. In: Proctor DL, editor. *Grain storage techniques: evolution and trends in developing countries*. Rome (Italy): FAO. p 89–134.

Relationship between relative humidity and moisture content at 43 °C.

Drying period (h)	Grain type			
	Rice		Maize	
	RH ^a (%)	MC ^b (% wb)	RH ^a (%)	MC ^b (% wb)
1	92	21.0	88	21.2
2	83	18.3	82	18.2
3	79	16.5	67	15.2
4	71	14.5	56	12.3
5	60	12.7	40	10.1
6	50	11.2	37	8.3
7	44	9.5	34	7.6
8	33	8.1	32	7.1
9	29	6.8	30	6.7
10	25	6.2	24	6.4
11	20	5.6	19	6.2

^aRH = relative humidity (%). ^bMC = moisture content (% wb, percent wet basis).